

How to Help Kurdish Students Learn English in Secondary School's First Year at Khormal Secondary School in Kurdistan, Iraq

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Article Information

Suggested Citation:

Ghafar, Z.N. (2023). How to Help Kurdish Students Learn English in Secondary School's First Year at Khormal Secondary School in Kurdistan-Iraq. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(3), 73-84.

DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(3\).08](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(3).08)

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Abstract:

English would seem to be the most fundamental language for communication and studying purposes. An educated Kurdish should be able to clearly explain their views and opinions, appropriately use foreign sources, and satisfy their requirements, since these are the aims of the curriculum for foreign language instruction in Kurdistan. Students must understand native-speaker English. Experts in English education design educational English books with these aims in mind, and teachers have used them for years to teach pupils. The qualitative method contains semi-structured interviews with 20 Kurdish pupils from two secondary schools in Khormal, Iraq, three teachers, 1 English supervisor, and several family students who were taken part in the study also questioned to get reliable data. The research addresses these questions: Why are Kurdish students

becoming disappointed with English subjects? Why don't they learn English? This study found that most secondary school students face these issues. The results show that 1. Many learners don't have a passing knowledge of the English language. 2. They often acknowledge that English is a challenging area of academic study. 3. They also believe that they will not make real advancements in their English language skills. 4. They do not comprehend English because they compare themselves to senior students. Using instructional tools, keeping students' enthusiasm for English, arranging instructional material from simple to complex, and seeking advice from professionals, parents, school officials, and students may be helpful. This research aims to explore students' and teachers' perceptions of English and inspire them to learn and teach the English language.

Keywords: *english language teaching, difficulties in english, first secondary grade, progress, students' perceptions.*

Introduction

English is taught as a second or foreign language in developing nations. This phrase has long been emphasized. Its importance rests in these parts: English proficiency aids cultural interactions, modern technology, significant changes, and employing scientific resources and new technologies need English skills. According to Iran's foreign language curriculum, English helps

students understand cultural exchanges and communicate human knowledge in verbal, audiovisual, and written settings. In teaching English to speakers of other languages, students often are not native speakers of the language (Chomsky, 1965). Teaching English as a foreign language (TEFL) often takes place in the student's native country, either in a public or private school or one-on-one with an instructor. One of the factors that contribute to the

challenge that is instructing a foreign language is exposure. The use of English should be reinforced often. Students find it challenging to use English as a foreign language since they cannot use it all the time and in all situations. The assumption made by the students is the other component. In addition, they do not need to be experts in their strategies to maintain within them. Teaching English as a foreign language is challenging work in developing nations in general and in our country in particular since it can serve its speakers, teaching and learning become more significant, as stated by Akbari (2015, p. 394-401). English is taught in schools in Iraq/Kurdistan, although not as much as in other underdeveloped nations. Despite adequate preparation, curriculum, textbooks, trained instructors, and efficient administration, skill development may make the teaching-learning process hopeless. Studying foreign languages satisfies the requirements of interpersonal and intercultural communication and contributes to the development of commerce, technology, science, and a knowledge of political and social issues.

The goals are to teach four languages and general communication skills. 1st high school pupils must read and understand medium-difficulty materials. The students who are now in the first year of their secondary education report lacking essential English-learning abilities. They are incapable of learning English. They are looking forward to a new obstacle. They are uncertain about their ability to pick up the English language. As a result, it is essential to critically assess and bring attention to these concerns while developing instructional strategies. Utilizing colleagues' experiences and having conversations with families, educational experts, advisors, and school authorities may be used to address these challenges and find solutions. Research conducted by Raja and Selvi (2011) suggests that there are a variety of elements that make learning a second language a challenging endeavor. Teachers of English need to get the appropriate education to successfully deliver academic lectures in settings where students are engaged in acquiring English as a second language. The flawed examination system is the

fundamental source of students' inadequate competency in their speaking skills because students concentrate all of their efforts on achieving high exam scores rather than cultivating their language abilities (Tufail et al. 2015).

According to a questionnaire intended to reflect the views of students in this grade, first-grader at students in secondary school, who have little to no background in English, believe that the subject is more complicated than mathematics because of this. Teachers and pupils do not benefit from this arrangement. As a result, I decided to alter the situation via research and communication with educational authorities to minimize the problem. Some students were questioned about doing this. A series of inquiries were set as follows:

1. Why do most first-year secondary school students detest learning and practicing English?
2. Why do some pupils have English homework struggles?
3. Why are some classmates anxious while answering English questions?
4. Why do some learners only perform homework when attempting to push?
5. Why don't most individuals connect English to their lives?
6. Why do they find learning English difficult, and why do they think they cannot learn it?

Every single student answered the questions that were asked. Even though most of the questions were given truthful responses, the answers seemed more like poor excuses for not making enough effort to study English and practice the language.

Literature Review

The purpose of this section was to investigate the challenges students face when studying the English language. In addition, it seeks to investigate the methods and means by researching other nations. Unfortunately, academic institutions in Kurdistan fail to recognize the importance of excellent English

language education, so students continue to struggle with the subject. Although students must take English as a required subject, the teaching methods do not meet the student's academic requirements. The researcher evaluated relevant literature in this area. He did this to comprehend the issue better. Once he is happy with his literary search, he organizes it. He prepared the research by subject and assessed how each connected to the situation. This study's goals give a foundation. Because the research has several goals, each is organized separately. Motivation is vital for effective foreign language learning, but there is less consensus on what it entails.

Motivation has been used as "a generic cover term- a dustbin- to comprise a variety of presumably separate notions" (Mc Donough, 1981, p. 143). The word "motivation" is often used in psychiatric, educational, and linguistic contexts, according to Vincent (1984). It refers to some complex ideas, including Maslow's hierarchy of demands, McLeland's focus on success, and Hull's drive reduction theory. At a deeper level, motivation encompasses notions like what piques someone's interest, retains their attention, or, most fundamentally, prompts them to do an action (p. 38). According to Arno (1981), motivation is any circumstance that begins, leads, and maintains behavior in an organism. For example, a little girl who is neither hungry nor thirsty may disregard a bottle of milk placed before her by her parents. Although she has learned to drink from a bottle, she will not do so if she is not motivated (p. 218)

Akujobi and Chukwu (2012) conducted a study that contends that various factors influence students' English learning, including their mother tongue, media, instructors' teaching experiences, diverse cultural backgrounds, and big classes. According to Akujobi (2012) and Dhillon&Wanjiru (2012), regional language influences English proficiency (2013). Vand (2012) stated in his study, "How could I make a disappointed student interested in English," that he finds studying English boring. Consequently, he aided in teaching English, altered the competitive aspects used in instruction, turned to admiring, motivating, and rewarded students

with presents, and lastly, noted and discussed in class the faults and strengths of each student.

As an outcome, students' attitudes about English as a foreign language improved. "Full homerooms may affect teaching and learning," says one English instructor (Emery, 2012). When class sizes are small, the general student population is large, the classroom walls are thin, and noise travels. Students sit together in extensive courses, presenting various issues, such as a lack of permanent tables and chairs. Teaching and learning need a pleasant and engaging setting; otherwise, instructors may not be able to achieve students' requirements and attain learning objectives (Nurkamto, 2003; Beckr and Westrup, 2000).

Teachers may not have specific resources or have damaged or insufficient inventory. This makes it more difficult for teachers to educate students successfully (Fatoro, 2015; Nurkamto, 2003). "Language can only be mastered via deliberate practice in the four linguistic skills" of hearing, speaking, reading, and writing (Pande, 2013, p. 417). It is essential to have access to instructional resources, and these materials should be given as promptly as possible. We need educational materials. According to (Fatoro, 2015), "Students' frightened attitude towards the use and use of English, particularly in the presence of a skilled user, is a most critical difficulty facing learners of English as a second language. Speaking English demand, a certain level of preparation and confidence. However, if a speaker feels unprepared, it may result in incoherence and improper language (p. 28).

According to a study by M. Behroozi et al. (2014), the under-studied curriculum has several significant flaws. Some of these flaws include unsuitable teaching patterns, poor facilities, and a lack of a practical perspective on learning English as a foreign language (Ediger, Celce-Murcia, Briton, Snow & Heinle, 2014). The similarities and differences between learning a second language and learning a first language, as well as the aspects of language and comprehension that educators should emphasize while instructing students in English, were examined in the study "Teaching

Second/Foreign Language Literacy to School-Age Learners." Additionally, in the manuscript "Tools and Techniques for Effective Second/Foreign Language Teaching," According to P. Pimsleur (1963), some students' poor performance in EFL lessons is primarily due to issues with their auditory skills, specifically issues with sound and sound-symbol acquisition, rather than a lack of intelligence or enthusiasm. Toolan (2009) believes that teaching may have numerous learning aids and techniques; the instructor should pick the best way for what they teach and the student's level. Learning chance. Students come from diverse socioeconomic levels and have varied thinking levels. Therefore, it is necessary to consider these distinctions to provide them with the same learning chance. People convey their wants and emotions via language. Kumar (2010) says that language is the most important social tool; we utilize it at home, work, and on the streets. Words constitute language; learning them helps us understand art. Scollon (2004) also discussed language's originality, speaking over writing, and human communication's universality. According to Holmes (1992), research on second language acquisition focuses on how newborns and bilingual individuals improve their language knowledge and use.

Educational tools should describe ideas, assist sense-making, engage pupils, and drive learning (Toptas, Çelik & Karaca, 2012). Textbooks, instructors' manuals, workbooks, maps, presentations, photographs, and CDs. Gurney (2007) suggests five classroom teaching elements: 1. Teacher knowledge, enthusiasm, and learning responsibility. Learning-promoting classroom activities. Key factor 3: Experiential assessment. Effective classroom feedback is ingredient 4. Effective instructor-student communication creates a healthy learning environment. An atmosphere that values, fosters, and enhances experiential learning. Teachers educate language process. The teacher must assist students in strengthening their language abilities. The instructor assesses the student's work to see how they are doing. The instructor must be organized. He should be an organized language teacher who knows what

works. To save time, he should not give learners worthless or unclear information. The instructor also prompts (Wang, 2010).

The research by Akasha (2013) determined that the curriculum was inadequately developed to suit the intellectual demands of students and that insufficient practical exercises were included to alleviate students' stress. Laghari et al. (2021) conducted research that supports the difficulties faced by English language learners and offers challenging strategies to overcome these difficulties to foster successful learning. Teachers of English, academicians, and directors should assist students in overcoming English language learning obstacles that impair their academic achievement in this dimension.

Empirical Study Review

Al-Dmour (2013) investigated "Problems of English Teaching for First Secondary Grade Students in Al-Karak Educational Directorates from Teachers' Perspective." The goal was to identify the issues associated with teaching English to first-year secondary students. Teachers' perspectives on pupils in Al-Karak educational directorates. The study sample consisted of sixty first-year secondary school instructors who completed a sixty-item questionnaire about teaching English to students. Concerning instructional issues, the findings revealed no statistically significant disparities between male and female first-year secondary English pupils. In addition, there were statistically significant variations in the difficulty of teaching English to children in the first year of secondary school, favoring older kids (5–10, 10 years and older) with English teachers who got Bachelor's and diploma degrees.

Khankar (2001) studied the English Language Curriculum's most significant issues for Taif's first secondary school students. The researcher created a questionnaire that addressed the most significant challenges that the curriculum's components (educational goals, curriculum, instructional techniques, the school calendar, extracurricular activities, the teacher's book, amenities, structures, and equipment) may encounter. Taif's English instructors, who were included in the study's 103-parameter worldwide

sample, received it. The study's findings revealed that there were numerous issues with the curriculum's components, including a lack of emphasis on cultural considerations, difficulties with the use of English outside of the classroom, a lack of engaging subject matter, and length that did not fit the time given, and material that does not support students' independent learning. The research also found that the English as a Second Language (ESL) program at a technical institution in the Southeast lacked assessment and had few modern teaching tools.

In the framework of a teaching practicum held in 14 different secondary schools in Bandung, Indonesia. Riesky (2013) studied the various teaching challenges and the actions taken to address them by English student instructors. The primary method of data collection for the researcher was interviewing. The study's sample included college students who participated in data collection as part of their coursework in an EFL methodology class. The study's findings showed that many issues might be divided into three categories: students, the person in charge of supervising instructors, and the future educators themselves. The majority of the issues related to how to control pupils' conduct, as the research shows. Second, student teachers' classroom challenges may be related to the supervising instructors' professional competence.

Additionally, it was discovered that student teachers whom certified teachers supervised had fewer student-related teaching challenges than those whom noncertified teachers supervised. However, this finding is ironic when considering the student teachers' high rate of self-related challenges. The survey also revealed that some student instructors still believe they have certain pedagogical shortcomings, particularly in managing the classroom, creating instructional materials, and using effective teaching tactics.

Al-Shirbini (1988) sought to determine the requirements for instructors to use interactive and conversational English methods. The researcher employed an experimental strategy to accomplish the study's objectives by creating a methodological course to fulfill the

communicative goal of English teacher training programs. The study's findings improved the way that technique and language were combined. Results also showed that the level of progress attained was related to the methods used in training programs. Through application and testing, they demonstrated the accuracy of the theoretical underpinnings of design. They claimed that this teaching method led to the high degrees that the students attained.

Wagari (2003) researched to analyze syllabus-related difficulties in secondary schools, finding classroom-related challenges faced by student instructors in the teaching-learning setting. Multi-stage stratified sampling was used to get the sample of student teachers, and two questionnaires were used to gather data from the sample of teaching practice assessors. Both questionnaires were shown to be valid. The results revealed that student teachers had difficulty applying the information to promote learning and that there were difficulties while planning lessons since student instructors were not exposed to the secondary school curriculum via the college program. Professional training was regarded as critical, but more was required, as well as more fantastic guidance on how and when to utilize instructional aids. Maintaining pupils' interest and motivation while ensuring good discipline provided some challenges for many student instructors.

Fakhri and Jdetawy (2011) conducted a literature study on Arab EFL learners' issues. According to the research, Arab EFL students struggle with reading, writing, and speaking. The study also identified the underlying causes of these issues, including the Arab EFL students' poor first-language English proficiency, their preference for using Arabic in EFL classes rather than English, their use of Arabic as their official language of communication, their lack of exposure to the target language as spoken by native speakers, their lack of participation in their language teaching context, and their lack of character.

The difficulties that instructors and students have while teaching and studying English at the secondary level are discussed in Teevno's (2011)

research. One class was included in the research. It has been noted that while the governments of Sindh and Pakistan have recently offered many facilities, such as free books and training courses for secondary school teachers, the teaching and study of English have not been up to par. Participants in the research comprised 70 students, 40 males and 30 females. 11 English instructors, seven males, and four females, and six English experts, four males and two females. Teachers and students were polled, organized focus groups, and interviewed experts. It was discovered that the curriculum did not meet the requirements of the pupils, the facilities were inadequate, and the staff lacked the required training for teaching English.

Methodology

The introduction section has already focused on the qualitative method containing six questions to show how everyone answered the questions. Even though most questions were answered truthfully, the answers appeared like excuses for not studying and practicing English. Questionnaires, book surveys, and the perspectives of students, coworkers, the principal, the sub-principal, consultants, specialists, and parents were used to assess the data. First, technical issues were found. The revisions, agreements, and performances were then specified. For gathering qualitative data, semi-structured interviews were conducted with 20 Kurdish pupils from two classes at the secondary school in Khurmal, Iraq, who took part in the study. 3 teachers, 1 English supervisor, and several family students were also questioned to get reliable data.

Theoretical Basis of the Research

At first, teachers, parents, and students were given individualized questions to answer so that researchers could investigate their children's family and educational histories. They were advised to respond objectively to put their suggestions into practice. An advisory board of English instructors was established to determine the causes behind students' lack interest in

English and their reluctance to complete their English assignments. There was a meeting that both principals and sub-principals attended. After obtaining significant experience, the assistant principals discussed their perspectives. As a result of the fact that they have been placed in a higher grade, new students feel as if they are being held to a higher standard the moment they enter the classroom, which causes them to struggle with the mental aspects of their education. A principal proposed bringing the issue before the schools' parents and administrators. A conference with a few parents, educational authorities, managers, a semi, and two student delegates was scheduled in response. Then we searched the numerous psychology and education libraries for information on pupils' mental and personality conditions. A poll looking at ways to increase self-confidence and build pupils' necessary skills was done with the help of an education professor. Some English instructors brought up the topic and conclusions at a local conference. Some helpful recommendations were made due to their excellent understanding of first-graders in secondary schools. The data were evaluated using questionnaires, book surveys, and student, colleague, principal, sub-principal, consultant, specialist, and parent viewpoints. First, technological problems were identified. Then, the changes, accords, and performances were defined. Facts may be categorized as follows:

The Perspectives of Teachers at Various Teaching Assistant Foundations

Perspectives those educators have on the study of educational psychology and the discipline it belongs to this.

They claimed that feelings of inadequacy and a lack of prospective self-confidence caused the students' struggles with English.

"I believe that a teacher may significantly influence how motivated pupils are to study English. Since most students believe that learning English is difficult, it is our responsibility as educators to dispel this misconception by paying more consideration to the requirements and attitudes of the students. I do not doubt that a teacher's personality and

teaching methods greatly influence whether or not a student enjoys learning English" (T 3).

The opinions of education faculty members

"I don't believe that all students in classrooms with diverse backgrounds will perceive English teachers as motivators. They will lose the weak pupils if they cater to the requirements of the strong students, and the opposite (T1).

They observed that it would be an ideal strategy to deal with this dilemma to give students a chance to develop and show off their skills in learning and communicating in English by allowing them to do so. They believed this would be one of the finest approaches to contract with it.

The views of teachers involved in the curriculum development process.

They believed that setting long-term objectives, taking advantage of opportunities, and developing strategic development plans would help them improve their English.

"I once received a call from a school administrator asking me to speak with him about a teacher many kids found unmotivating. My investigation led me to conclude that the students' criticism stemmed from the teacher's focus on teaching the language rather than teaching for testing, which the students are seeking" (T2).

The Students' Points of View

All students interviewed stated they prefer learning English for practical reasons, including enhancing their careers and continuing their studies.

How bright students see things

A learner can improve their English skills and acquire outstanding results. After reaching a particular score, fear of English will become meaningless and no longer serve any purpose. The English class is similar to the other classes.

"I want to be a doctor. Without knowing English, how would I keep up with current advancements in medicine?" (S1).

"For pupils failing an English proficiency exam, pursuing further education in Kurdistan Universities or higher institutes becomes difficult (S4)".

"As a result of my desire to communicate with non-Kurdish speakers about Islam's generosity and the Kurds' peaceful character in English, as our faith encourages us to do (S 8)".

The attitudes of students who are considered to be average:

Students may learn English well if they put in more study time. However, this group feels that English novels seem to include fresh ideas. They assert that they do not have a solid English educational background. They said that if their professors or peers backed them, they could get high grades. When given the proper circumstances, they are ready to learn English.

To spread the word about the fundamental tenets of our faith, we need to learn English. (S3).

"I study English to comprehend how other people see Islam and Kurd culture" (S15).

Poor students' views

They clarified, "We have no prior experience with English classes. It seems that we are unable to learn English. English is undoubtedly a challenging subject. We cannot interpret it with our eyes, ears, or tongues." They believe that course to be among the hardest. Naturally, they do not value their skills and capabilities.

I find it challenging to acquire the English meanings of dozens of vocabulary words since I don't know how to achieve them (S18).

"I become upset and worried by the lengthy lists of new vocabulary terms I need to know to succeed in the English test" (S7).

"When I often discover that I cannot follow or comprehend the recorded talks and materials, I feel ashamed and demotivated" (S13).

"When I neglect my notebooks or don't respond to his inquiries, my teacher typically becomes upset and agitated" (S20).

"My followers don't like the procedure that my teacher uses to introduce each English lesson, which is "open your books page and read the lesson quietly". Additionally, the teacher rejects using Kurdish throughout the English class" (S 11).

"Our teacher humiliates and degrades us since he often reads out the exam results in front of the entire class, which leads the high scorers to tease the students who did poorly on the test or received low scores" (S13).

Families' Perceptions

The viewpoints of parents with higher levels of education

They mentioned that before their children entered elementary schools, they allegedly purchased many illustrated books for them. They have some familiarity with English idioms and terms. Some parents claimed their kids had enrolled in English lessons in elementary school. Although the others have studied English throughout their academic careers, they said their children have a fundamental understanding of the language.

Views of parents with lower educational backgrounds

After learning about the future relevance of English, parents have tried to offer their children what they want and need, as well as what others recommend. Financial restrictions and a lack of chances prevented their children from learning English. They promised to assist their kids' English.

The perceptions of uneducated parents

They have some understanding of the significance of English. Nobody could help their English-speaking children. They may have considered Math and Science essential, but not English. "We want to enhance English learning activities and promote English literacy,"

The Points of View Expressed by Coworkers

The opinions of teachers in different classes

They felt that the student's lack of familiarity with English during the first few months of the school year contributed to their perception that learning English was challenging. To adequately educate students mentally and intellectually,

which in turn enables them to discover and develop their identities in English, a tremendous amount of time and effort must be committed to the task. However, children with outstanding skills acquire knowledge more quickly and may be set in motion by studying English; hence, these pupils need to be motivated to study English.

Pedagogical advisers' attitudes in schools

They highlighted the need for all of us to have patience and provide inspiration to the pupils. We are obligated to guide them while also representing their capabilities to them. The relationship between English instructors and their pupils should be one of warmth and friendship at all times. Kindness and compassion should be shown to the kids by the English instructors.

The points of view held by English teachers

Their concerns included the following: Since the students have never studied English, we must finally expose them to it. English instructors must explain the worth and place of English, among other topics, as well as their lives and education. The interest in English may be boosted via engaging and energetic lessons.

Results and Discussion

According to the results of the research conducted on the English course's curriculum, framework, and timetable, it seems that the dispositions of the students should be used to determine how English lessons should be structured and allocated; students should take English classes whenever they feel like they have plenty of energy to devote to the subject. In addition, the information covered in English textbooks needs to advance logically from simple to complex, beginning with the most accessible topics. According to Khalili (2003) and Maleki (2010), instructors are the ones who should choose the degree of difficulty of the content and where it should be put in the book. Additionally, the outcomes based on effort and originality in English classrooms might be divided into three groups:

1. Encouraging and preserving a vast range of English teaching techniques. It is essential to avoid using the same teaching methods for the topic and its many components.

2. Educators should build and deepen student excitement for English by using help education items and unique recommendations and functions.

3. According to Geminian (2004), every student and subject should be given a specific instructional resource.

The studies on awareness and education show that students are encouraged and motivated by applause. Correct schooling improves learning. Using different learning and grading techniques and dividing students boost motivation. Using movies, songs, books, and other English works in different situations shows how important English is in their lives and helps them form user perceptions (Seif, 2003).

Here are some of the most important things that were found:

1. Many students misunderstand that English is one of the most challenging courses to master.

2. The pupils are not optimistic about their capacity to learn English uncompromisingly.

3. The learners do not think they have the ability or inherent talent to learn English.

4. Before they attend secondary school, the students have little to no exposure to the English language.

5. Most students have not signed up for English training courses at private English Schools.

6. Some parents have a limited educational background.

7. Throughout the first several months of the school year, they develop an inferiority complex and often compare themselves to intelligent classmates.

8. Students show unwillingness to complete the English homework projects they have been given.

9. Teachers typically create a competitive classroom environment, engaging both weak and outstanding students.

10. Students often fail to recognize the usefulness and significance of English in their lives and the impact that the language will have on their lives in the future.

The data show that first-graders in secondary schools need particular instruction to achieve their academic objectives., but they struggle with English ideas. They are also not enthusiastic about studying English and are unaware of their talents. Regarding various topic concerns, distinctive and appropriate actions must be evaluated. The findings imply that this issue manifests in unique dimensions and takes varied forms. Some situations need significant, ongoing, primary efforts, while others may be accomplished with little energy. Answers were carefully selected. Parents, coworkers, and students helped solve the situation. After this stage's activities were complete, a collection of replies containing the following conclusions were employed (these solutions were used in the first two educational months, namely October and November).

1. Changed content organization (contents ranged from easy to complex.)

2. English courses were filled with a desire to erase horrors.

3. The assistance education items were used in a manner that was appropriate for the themes.

4. The phrase "act and effort" was sometimes used to motivate students. "Neither you nor I may be aware of it. Let us jointly discover the solution.

5. During two months, it was assumed that students would participate actively in the instruction process.

6. A significant amount of innovation and use was put into the many forms of praise.

Conclusion

The results of this research showed that the students who took part in it achieved

significantly greater levels of learning. Furthermore, the action research approach was used as a research methodology to effectively address and resolve the issues that the students were going through. The adoption of action plans helped English language learners overcome the difficulties they faced in their studies. In addition, the findings of this research gave helpful insights that assisted students in enhancing their command of the English language. As a direct result of this research, individualized lesson plans were developed, some of which underwent revisions based on future courses. The findings of this research were beneficial to the academic and professional development of teachers and students working in education. After gathering information on adopting solutions and results and presenting it based on comments and critiques made during the regional conference, reports to the invited parties identified and addressed the hypothetical and applied flaws in the plan. These reports were given after the regional conference. Some students could obtain a high level of scientific English by working together and participating in cooperative games. The strategy and how things operate well were discussed in a conference with the school's press group. Among the outcomes are.

(i) The parents were overjoyed and thrilled to see how much their youngsters' English had improved.

(ii) The students concluded that English plays a crucial role in their day-to-day lives and futures.

(iii) The students determined that learning English is one of the most specific topics and one of the most exciting subjects.

(iiii) Nearly all students completed their English homework individualistically, including formulating and answering the questions. They could start small-group conversations in English and participate in them.

Recommendations

The researcher recommends that families expose their children to certain English words and

phrases as soon as they enroll in elementary school. Additionally, The children s English will improve if parents have the funds to enroll them in English classes at schools or other institutions. Families may expose their children to books that teach English via activities and books with pictures accompanying words and phrases. Introducing English to pupils in third and fourth grades is acceptable since teaching English in primary schools necessitates utilizing both natural techniques (games) and assistance instructional items and resources. Families often watch English-language films with their kids to help them learn the language. If so, the kids will have thinking and imaginative abilities as they age. They will exhibit feelings of confidence and self-worth. This approach will work well and be engaging while teaching other topics.

The following information should be considered and confirmed by instructors and students when English is being taught as a foreign language in the Kurdistan region of Iraq in light of the conclusion stated above.

1. Teachers should improve teaching aids, and those that cannot be improved should be acquired by the administration or school officials.

2. Teachers should keep up to speed on new teaching strategies by reading books. This should serve as a complement to their academic credentials.

3. English as foreign language instructors must be given fewer teaching times each week to have more opportunities to prepare for their classes and hand out assignments, which they will need to grade along with the pieces students write.

4. As a reward for their various exercises, English language instructors must be provided specific compensation.

5. It is essential to encourage teachers to participate in ongoing professional development opportunities, such as seminars and refresher courses focused on the English language classroom.

6. The study results are up to date with the rest of the field. The government must provide a platform through which such conversations may

occur between researchers and educators of the English language.

7. Students should be encouraged to participate in exciting activities by establishing school groups, such as literary or writer's clubs or dramatic organizations.

8. More openings must be made available for individuals interested in receiving training to become English language instructors. This will allow for the production of more English language instructors, which is necessary given the massive number of students enrolled in our institution.

9. It is crucial to include librarian time into the schedule so that kids can go to the library and review various reading resources.

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